

Teachers' Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies as Predictors of Students' Interest in Learning English

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Abstract. The study investigated the influence of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies on the student's interest in learning English. The researcher selected 156 elementary school teachers in Bunawan District, Davao City, as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies were moderately extensive, while students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City was extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City. Regression analysis proved that teachers' Interactive-direct teaching strategies regarding classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, learning attention, and a conducive environment significantly influenced the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City. Future researchers may engage in action research projects that involve collaboration with educators and policymakers to implement and evaluate innovative language education strategies. The study, therefore, was conducted further to utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching English
2. Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies
3. students' interest in learning English

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1. Introduction

Interest in learning is a concept that often arises when creating suitable learning environments for all students. It concerns the fundamental question of why students behave as they do and is one of the essential factors in second language learning and acquisition. That process of interest in learning English significantly influences some students who can obtain English skills. The students have to master all English skills either actively or passively. Students can be stressed because of the many skills that must be mastered in learning English. The interest to learn (a mental ability) is often connected to motivation and is expressed in some learning activities. The English language is essential in our lives as it helps us

communicate. It is the primary language used to study any subject worldwide. English is important for students as it broadens their minds, develops emotional skills, and improves their quality of life by providing job opportunities. Hayikaleng (2016) noted that students with a high interest in learning English will spend their time fully in the classroom activity, thus increasing their engagement in learning English. In addition, Chumbley et al. (2015) mentioned that students with a high interest in learning are more betrothed in acquisition and do practical tasks more entirely than those with low interest. According to Chinappi (2015), students interested in learning tend to engage in classroom activities and achieve the learning goal because they pay attention and use their time effectively during teaching and learning in the class. Moreover, Zeidan and Jayosi (2015) reported that students interested in learning can quickly understand complex concepts presented in the class. Hence, the school is supposed to enhance students' engagement and motivation by encouraging them to take initiative and actively participate in their learning processes. This implication of the teachers' interactive-direct teaching ability to affect factors related to the students makes learning interest a crucial task for teachers (and even students). According to Yildirim (2014), interactive-direct teaching strategies create a student-centered environment where students support each other's learning and construct knowledge using information resources and various tools to solve problems or reach their learning goals. In such a classroom, Tunca (2015) noted that teachers provide experience with the knowledge-constructing process, meaning learners gain experience constructing knowledge. Kwan and Wong (2014) concluded that one of the main aims of constructivism is developing critical thinking via experiences; thus, organizing a classroom environment aligned with interactive-direct learning environment characteristics can effectively support critical thinking.

On the one hand, previous investigations show that the interactive-direct teaching approach is linked to an interest in learning English among students. The study conducted by Cetin-Dindar (2016) showed that interactive-direct teaching strategies enhance students' interest in learning English using student-centered approaches. The interactive-direct teaching approach develops students to interact with knowledge and each other using various tools and emphasizes the learning environment where learning occurs rather than instruction itself. Also, Jorde and Dillon (2012) noted that in an interactive-direct learning environment, the teacher is a facilitator and guides students to achieve learning goals through interactive-direct teaching approaches; students freely voice their thoughts and share their opinions. On the other hand, research indicated that poor interest in learning English remains a perennial concern among young and adolescent students worldwide (Jin, 2014). As a fact, the report of Lasagabaster et al. (2014) showed that less interest in learning English is closely related to lower scores on achievement tests and grades. For instance, most of these students had difficulties in language learning, as evidenced by low performance. Similarly, Wimolmas (2012) reported that low interest in learning English resulted in the students' lack of interest in pursuing language-related courses. Likewise, Thapa (2011) asserted that those students' poor academic performance is due to their not trying to learn and not wanting to do extra labor, resulting in poor interest in learning. Although previous investigations (Cetin-Dindar, 2016; Jorde Dillon, 2012) showed a link between interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English, those studies were limited to a few aspects. First, studies that explore the relationship between these variables are scarce in the Philippine setting. Second, it was found that most of the studies utilized a qualitative approach. In this context, using a quantitative approach, the researcher needed to fill in the

research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Bunawan District, Davao City. Specifically, the researcher used a descriptive-correlational design to understand the students' interest in learning English better, as determined by the teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the student's interest in learning English in the context of students in Bunawan District, Davao City. The results of this study may be of interest to other researchers as they could provide valuable knowledge for their research.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies*—Interactive-direct teaching strategies combine interactive and direct teaching methods to engage students while providing structured guidance. This approach balances teacher explanations and student-centered activities, promoting clear communication and active student involvement (Yıldırım, 2014; Tunca, 2015; Anagün, 2018). Students participate in discussions and hands-on activities, which cater to diverse learning styles and needs (Ahmad et al., 2015; Mutlu Güler, 2017). Regular feedback helps assess understanding and adjust instruction (Gurses et al., 2015).

In interactive-direct environments, both teachers and students share responsibilities, fostering critical thinking and collaborative learning (Alkin, 2013; Alzahrani Woollard, 2013; Ndon, 2012; Cooper White, 2012). These classrooms support student expression and holistic learning experiences (Alt, 2016; Milner et al., 2012; McDougall, 2015). Assessment in such settings involves observations, exhibitions, and portfolios, focusing on reflective and creative thinking (Cirik et al., 2013; Evans, 2014; Lund Hauge, 2012).

1.1.2. *Students' Interest in Learning English*—Students' interest in learning English involves attraction, curiosity, and enthusiasm for

the language, leading to better engagement and outcomes (Glynn et al., 2012; Cardelús, 2015; Andersson, 2017). This interest fosters cross-cultural understanding and a sense of global citizenship, facilitating social connections and networking opportunities (Wiliam, 2011; Chan Norlizah, 2017; Chumbley et al., 2015).

An interest in English often becomes a life-long pursuit, engaging students with cultural works and personal growth (Albalate et al., 2018; Zeidan Jayosi, 2015). Students who see high value in learning English are more motivated and engaged, setting specific goals and working towards language proficiency (Tuan et al., 2005; Altındağ Senemoğlu, 2013; Granito Chernobilsky, 2012).

1.1.3. *Indicators of Teaching Strategies and Interest*—Conducive Environment: Effective management of classroom space and resources enhances student engagement and learning (Yıldırım, 2014; Savas Gurel, 2014; Tomlinson Jarvis, 2014; Agbabi et al., 2013; Blazar, 2016). Performance Goal: Setting clear objectives and regular progress monitoring lead to better language proficiency and satisfaction (Tuan et al., 2005; Guido Dela Cruz, 2011; Akomolafe Adesua, 2015; Michaelis, 2015). Skills Development: Interactive teaching promotes strong communication, teamwork, and study skills (Yıldırım, 2014; Harding, 2019; Alsaleh, 2020; Panadero, 2017; Aregu, 2013; Laurillard, 2012). Learning Environment Simulation: Designing optimal learning environments enhances engagement and motivation (Tuan et al., 2005; Akomolafe Adesua, 2015; Taylor, 2014). Learning Engagement: High engagement encourages curiosity and exploration beyond the curriculum, connecting new knowledge with existing concepts (Gee, 2013; Kober, 2015; Kelly, 2014). By integrating these strategies, teachers can significantly boost students' interest and performance in learning English.

1.2. *Synthesis*—Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher with the re-

sults of other research to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. More so, the literature showed that the constructivist instructional approach, as proposed by Yıldırım (2014), is measured in terms of communication and interaction, relation establishment, skills development, time usage and assessment, learning and teaching, and learning environment organization. Meanwhile, as contextualized by Tuana et al. (2005), academic motivation is indicated by self-efficacy, active learning strategies, science learning values, performance goals, achievement goals, and learning environment simulations. Interactive teaching was used to teach methods that engage the classroom. Unlike memorization, interactive teaching encourages students and teachers to collaborate to foster learning. Interactive learning is a hands-on approach to helping students become more engaged and retain more material. With or without a form of technology, interactive learning helps students strengthen problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Hence, the above literature review helped the researcher establish the conceptual and theoretical framework by explicitly discussing the nature of variables, the choice of population, and the method to answer the research objectives identified. It also provides the basis for the interpretation of data. In addition, reviews of the literature suggested that there are limited indicators of a constructivist instructional approach that were indisputably associated with the academic motivation of the learners.

*1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—*The study is anchored on Dörnyei and Csizér's (1998) Motivational Strategies, which focus on teaching actions and moments that motivate students to engage in the second-language classroom. According to Dörnyei and Csizér (1998), the characteristics of the model are broad recommendations that teachers can apply to increase students' interest in language learning. They were quite practical, and their usage and ef-

ficacy could result in differing outcomes depending on contextual, cultural, and even educational factors and settings surrounding the circumstances in which they are used. In support, Ogden (2017) postulated that teaching-related factors like the teacher's leadership ability, didactic skills in effectively communicating the subject content to students, and relationship building and fostering ability and engagement are also highlighted as having a high impact on student's performance to a great extent. Accordingly, some of these aspects include the teacher's specific characteristics, such as the acts and personality and the teaching situation created by the teacher. Adding more, good relations between the teacher and his or her students, the teacher's (high) expectations of all students, the teacher's ability to focus on what is essential in the teaching, and even sound and properly timed feedback. The study was also anchored on Constructivist Theory by Piaget (1968), which indicates that humans create knowledge by interacting with their experiences and ideas. The view of constructivism inspires radical constructivism because he believes that the individual is at the center of the knowledge creation and acquisition process. This intention and their perceptions of capability determine their likelihood of performing this behavior. The theory implies that social phenomena and categories are not only produced through social interaction but are constantly revised. In other words, this position reflects understanding a phenomenon via the perspective of those who live it and make sense of it. Moreover, Cetin-Dindar (2016) posited that a constructivist learning environment enhances learners' interaction with knowledge and each other using various tools and emphasizes the learning environment where learning occurs rather than instruction itself. In a constructivist learning environment, the teacher is a facilitator and guides learners to achieve learning goals. Through constructivist teaching approaches, learners freely voice their

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

thoughts and share their opinions. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The study's independent variable is teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies or the set of skills that help create a student-centered environment where learners support each other's learning and construct knowledge by using information resources and various tools to solve a problem or reach their learning goals. The measures of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies, according to Yıldırım (2014), are classroom interaction or the reciprocal actions that take place in a room, in a school, between the teacher and the students; learning engagement or the extent to which the teachers engage with learners in direct experience and focused reflection; skills development or the process wherein the students use cognitive skills or strategies that increase the probability of a desirable learning outcome in constructivist learning environment; time consciousness or the extent in which students organized their schedule in such a way that they achieve their goals efficiently and effectively; learning attention or the ability of the teacher to use strategies that attract

students attention and keep them on tasks; and conducive environment or the teachers' ability to cooperatively manage space, resources, and students' roles and behaviors. The dependent variable of this study was the student's interest in learning English or the set of processes concerned with a force that energizes behavior and directs it toward it. The measures of students' interest in learning English are self-efficacy or the belief in one's own ability to perform well in learning tasks; active learning strategies or the use of a variety of strategies to construct new knowledge based on their previous understanding; learning value or the acquisition of problem-solving efficiency, mastery the investigation prosperity, shake they're taking into consideration and find the pertinence of humanities with daily life; performance goal or the goal to compete with other students and get attention from the teacher; and learning environment stimulation which refers to a scenario in the class, wherein learning neighborhood surrounding students, such as course, teachers' instruction, and pupil interaction influenced students' motivation in humanities learning.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary aim of this study was to determine which domains of teachers' interactive-direct teaching

strategies significantly influence the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of:

- (1) Classroom Interaction;
 - (2) Learning Engagement;
 - (3) Skills Development;
 - (4) Time Consciousness;
 - (5) Learning Attention; and
 - (6) Conducive Environment?
- (2) What is the extent of students' interest in learning English in terms of:
- (1) self-efficacy;
 - (2) active learning strategies;
 - (3) learning values;
 - (4) performance goal; and
 - (5) learning environment simulation?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City?
- (4) Which domain of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies significantly influences the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City?

1.5. *Hypothesis*—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City. H02: None of the domains of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies significantly influence students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City. The current study would generate social value because it contributes to educational and sociological study in three critical ways. This study may benefit identified sectors of the academe in the Philippines. School Administrator. The study's outcome may provide the school administrator with an understanding of the seriousness of increasing interest in learning English among students in society nowadays, especially in the elementary school context. Lack of interest in learning is something that every teacher encounters during his or her teaching career. This may serve as the basis for the school administrators to send teachers to training and seminars in or-

der for the teacher to increase students' ability by paying attention to students' wishes based on their motivation. Teachers. The teacher must know how students are motivated to improve their ability to learn English. When a teacher already knows how to increase students' interest, it may be easier for the teacher to approach when teaching English in class so students can take lessons with pleasant feelings. Besides that, it could help teachers to make plans to teach effective English. The teacher can also find out that students who have an interest in learning English when learning can absorb lessons better than students who are not motivated. Therefore, the teacher must continue to stimulate students so that the motivation to learn English appears. Future Researchers. Prospective researchers are expected to conduct the same research in a broader population and sample because other levels of institutions would have different results. However, this thesis would still help contribute to and provide information to future researchers so that the developers of other English education can also feel the advantages and benefits.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher used the quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique to achieve the study's objectives and gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) defined quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach that emphasizes testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher investigated the relationship between two variables—the relationship between teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English. In this connection, the study focused on the relationships between these variables to determine the significance of the relationship. In this study, using descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents and did not perform an experiment in a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Bunawan District, Davao City. The 156 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling was appropriate in this study because there was heterogeneity in a population that could be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The following are the inclusion criteria: teachers with a minimum of 3 years of experience in teaching English; teachers with at least a bachelor's degree in English or a related field; teachers with a high level of proficiency in English to ensure effective communication and instruction in the language; and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the teachers' socio-economic status and performance rating.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed researcher-made questionnaires to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The first part of the instrument is concerned with the teachers’ teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies. The instrument was composed of

statements divided into indicators: classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, time development, time consciousness, learning attention, and conducive environment. The questionnaire made use of a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following range of mean:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies are often observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies are sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies are seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies are never observed.

The second part of the instrument is about interest in learning English. The questionnaire comprised self-efficacy statements, active learning strategies, learning values, performance goals, and learning environment goals. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.947, which was interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and con-

sistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of students’ interest in learning English, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The student’s interest in learning English is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The student’s interest in learning English is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The student’s interest in learning English is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The student’s interest in learning English is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The student’s interest in learning English is never manifested.

The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. *Permission to Conduct the Study.* The researcher obtained permission to conduct the study and gained endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. The endorsement letter from the Dean was attached to the permission letters, which were then forwarded for endorsement to the school's division superintendent and subsequently to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Bunawan District, Division of Davao City. *Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire.* After the study was approved, the researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents. The study was conducted in the first quarter of S.Y. 2023-2024. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the questionnaire administration, the researcher adhered to compliance with Health protocols issued by both local and national authorities. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. *Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data.* After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The

survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. *Informed Consent.* The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were adequately informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were provided so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate. It was made clear that the respondent's involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, the researcher did not force them. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to study the factors that hinder/promote the students' interest in learning English and about teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies that may contribute to the enhancement. *Vulnerability of Research Participants.* The study's respondents are learners, so they are considered vulnerable since all of them are not yet of legal age. They are also considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey would be set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. *Privacy and Confidentiality.* This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the natural source of information, to protect the respondents' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the participants, who were

the natural source of information.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools the researcher utilized in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies) and

dependent (students' interest in learning English) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Multiple linear regression was applied to evaluate the significance of the influence of the independent (teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies) variable on the dependent (students' interest in learning English) variable. This was utilized to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City; the significant relationship between teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies and students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City; and the influence of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies on the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City.

3.1. Teachers' Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies—

3.1.1. *Classroom Interaction*—Table 1 shows that the respondents assessed the teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies regarding classroom interaction as moderately extensive with a category mean of 3.21, interpreted as sometimes observed in Bunawan District, Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.26 to 4.19. On the one hand, the item Encouraging me to communicate using English both with me and each other has a mean rating of 4.19, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the respondents. On the other hand, the item Encouraging me to be enterprising reflects a mean of 2.26 described as less extensive and

interpreted as seldom observed by the teachers. This implies that the balanced and purposeful communication exchange between teachers and students is sometimes observed in Bunawan District, Davao City. The result agrees with the view of Bawa and Zubairu (2015) that a two-way flow of communication characterizes interaction in the classroom. Teachers provide information, guidance, and explanations while students actively engage by responding, asking questions, and expressing their thoughts. This also supports the idea of Hurst et al. (2013) that teachers use interaction to ensure that students understand the material. They provide immediate feedback to correct misconceptions and reinforce learning. Students also seek clarification when they encounter difficulties.

3.1.2. *They are learning Engagement*—Results in Table 2 show that the teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in learn-

ing engagement got an extensive category mean rating of 3.41, meaning that the teachers in Bunawan District, Davao City, often observe

Table 1. Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Terms of Classroom Interaction

#	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Taking students’ opinions into account when discussing topics in English.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
2.	Encouraging students to take the floor, to speak and to discuss to express their opinions regarding the topic discussed in English.	3.50	Extensive
3.	Encouraging me to be enterprising.	2.26	Less Extensive
4.	Encouraging me to give decision skills of the students.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
5.	Encouraging me to communicate using English both with me and each other.	4.19	Extensive
6.	Supporting the development of the feeling of responsibility in the students.	3.45	Extensive
7.	In English class, students should be included in rule-making and decision-making processes.	2.56	Moderately Extensive
8.	Supporting the development of self-discipline skills in the students.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.21	Moderately Extensive

this domain. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.25 to 4.21. The item giving feedback to the students in English class reflects a mean rating of 4.21, which is described as very extensive and interpreted as an item always observed. Meanwhile, the item Guiding the students to give meaning to what they learn in English class 2.25 is described as less extensive and interpreted as an item seldom observed by the teachers.

Table 2. Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Terms of Learning Engagement

#	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Giving feedback to the students in English class.	4.21	Very Extensive
2.	Giving students the opportunity to establish a relationship between what they learn in English and the facts and concepts in nature.	3.27	Moderately Extensive
3.	Asking open-ended questions that provoke thinking in the students.	3.32	Moderately Extensive
4.	Guiding the students to give meaning to what they learn in English class.	2.25	Less Extensive
5.	Stimulating the prior knowledge and previous experiences of students in order to facilitate the construction of knowledge in English class.	4.00	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.41	Extensive

This means students are enthusiastic, self-directed learners who actively participate, collaborate, and strive for a deep understanding of the subject matter. This environment fosters a love for learning and equips students with valuable skills and knowledge that extend beyond the classroom. The result agrees with Agsalog’s (2019) proposition that students actively engage in class activities, discussions, and tasks. They willingly participate in classroom activities and contribute to discussions. They are internally motivated to learn. They are genuinely interested in the subject matter and find personal value in their studies. This supports the assertion of Gee (2013) that extensive learning engagement encourages students to ask questions, seek answers, and explore topics beyond what is covered in the curriculum. They exhibit a

natural curiosity about the subject.

3.1.3. Skill Development—Teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of skill development acquired a category mean of 3.27, described as moderately extensive, which means that the teachers in Bunawan District, Davao City sometimes observe it. Table 3 further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 2.56 to 4.18. It is noteworthy that supporting the development of high-level thinking skills of the students has a mean rating of 4.18, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes observed, while the item Supporting the development of information access and the usage English language skills of the students has a mean rating of 2.56, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes observed by the respondents.

Table 3. Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Terms of Skill Development

#	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Supporting the development of question asking, questioning, and research skills.	3.02	Moderately Extensive
2.	Supporting the development of high-level thinking skills of the students.	4.18	Extensive
3.	Supporting the development of the problem-solving skills of the learners.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
4.	Supporting the development of information access and the usage of English language skills of the students.	2.56	Less Extensive
5.	Supporting the development of information access and the usage of English language skills of the students.	3.42	Extensive
6.	Supporting the development of purpose determination and the realization skills of the students.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.27	Moderately Extensive

This implies that students acquire subject-specific knowledge and a wide range of valuable skills. This supports Harding’s (2019) idea that students should be encouraged to develop strong communication skills, including effective speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Class discussions, presentations, and written as-

signments contribute to this development. Additionally, this supports Alsaleh’s (2020) that interactive activities and group projects promote the development of teamwork and collaboration skills. Students learn to work effectively with others, share responsibilities, and communicate within a team.

3.1.4. *Time Consciousness*—Results in Table 4 show that teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of time consciousness got an extensive category mean rating of 3.45, which is often observed in Bunawan District, Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.15 to 3.77. The item encouraging students to use the time efficiently

and effectively reflects a mean rating of 3.77, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed. Meanwhile, the item considering the learning process of the students, rather than the results in the assessment, shows a rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes observed by the respondents.

Table 4. Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Terms of Time Consciousness

#	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Giving the students the necessary time to answer the questions.	3.65	Extensive
2.	Giving the students enough time in English learning activities.	3.19	Moderately Extensive
3.	Encouraging students to use their time efficiently and effectively.	3.77	Extensive
4.	Using different assessment techniques to evaluate the students.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
5.	Taking the learning process of the students into consideration rather than the results in the assessment.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
6.	Encouraging the students to make self-assessments.	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.45	Extensive

This suggests that the heightened awareness of time as a valuable and limited resource within the classroom is oftentimes observed. It emphasizes efficient time management for instructional activities, student engagement, and learning outcomes. This supports Obijiaku’s (2015) idea that teachers meticulously plan and organize their lessons, ensuring they are focused, coherent, and well-structured. Clear learning objectives are established to guide the efficient use of time. They are skilled at pacing their lessons effectively. They allocate appropriate amounts of time to different activities, ensuring that no single task dominates the class. Adding more, the result agrees with Clark’s (2014) idea that teachers provide timely and constructive feedback to students.

3.1.5. *Learning Attention*—Results in Table 5 show that teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies in learning attention got a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.32, sometimes observed in Bunawan District, Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.90 to 4.17. The item Conducting the English lesson by focusing on main concepts reflects a mean rating of 4.17, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed. Meanwhile, the item Devising English learning activities for the students’ active learning shows a rating of 2.90, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes observed by the respondents. This suggests that students are engaged, focused, and attentive during learning. The result corroborates Temli-Dumus’s (2016)

idea that teachers’ interactive-direct teaching at moderate levels involves creating an environment where students are sufficiently engaged, focused, and attentive to the instructional content and activities. It balances teacher guidance and student participation to sustain interest and

concentration. This also supports the assertion of Llego (2017) that active learning strategies, such as problem-solving, case studies, and debates, are incorporated to keep students engaged through participation and hands-on experiences.

Table 5. Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Terms of Learning Attention

#	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Conducting the English lesson by focusing on main concepts.	4.17	Extensive
2.	Using various teaching methods and techniques which are consistent with the lesson’s purpose.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3.	Devising some activities in the lesson to attract student attention and to increase participation in English class.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
4.	Devising English learning activities for the active learning of the students.	2.90	Moderately Extensive
5.	Centering learning around students’ English interests and needs.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.32	Moderately Extensive

3.1.6. *Conducive Environment*—Teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of a conducive environment acquired a category mean of 3.53, described as moderately extensive, which is sometimes observed by the teachers in Bunawan District, Davao City. Table 6 further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 2.96 to 4.02. It is noteworthy that Presenting real-life problems or unsolved incidents to the students has a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes observed, while the item Prepare an order of seating which facilitates the communication and interaction among the students has a mean rating of 2.96, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes observed by the respondents. This implies that the classroom environment provides a support-

ive, engaging, and responsive atmosphere for learning. It is designed to foster student motivation, participation, and overall well-being. This is congruent with Savas and Gurel’s (2014) idea that a conducive classroom environment contributes to an overall positive school experience for students, which can increase their satisfaction and engagement in the educational process. It provides the necessary conditions for students to flourish academically, emotionally, and socially. When students feel safe, supported, and engaged, they are more likely to reach their full potential and develop into well-rounded individuals ready to meet future challenges. Adding more, the result supports the idea of Tomlinson and Jarvis (2014) that a well-designed classroom that promotes engagement and active learning helps students better absorb and retain information.

Table 6. Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Terms of Conducive Environment

#	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Presenting real-life problems or unsolved incidents to the students.	4.02	Extensive
2.	Making learning possible outside of the school as well as in it.	3.89	Extensive
3.	Using various real materials and primary sources to support the participation.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
4.	Preparing an order of seating which facilitates the communication and interaction among the students.	2.96	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.53	Extensive

Lastly, Table 7 shows the teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies in Bunawan District, Davao City. It shows that the overall mean of teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies is 3.36, which is moderately extensive and sometimes observed. In addition, teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of a conducive environment acquired the highest mean score of 3.53, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies regarding classroom interaction got the lowest mean score of 3.21, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents in Bunawan District, Davao City.

Table 7. Summary of Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies in Bunawan District, Davao City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Classroom Interaction	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Learning Engagement	3.41	Extensive
Skills Development	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Time Consciousness	3.45	Extensive
Learning Attention	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Conducive Environment	3.53	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

This suggests that the balance between teacher guidance and student involvement falls somewhere in the middle, offering a well-rounded approach to instruction. The result corroborates Anagün’s (2018) assertion that teachers balance direct instruction and student-centered activities in a moderate level of interactive-direct teaching. This means that teachers provide clear explanations and instructions when necessary and allow students to take ownership of their learning. Teachers maintain clear and effective communication with students. They ensure that students understand the lesson’s content, objectives, and expectations. This also supports the idea of Ahmad et al. (2015) that in interactive-direct teaching strategies, students are actively engaged in the learning process. They can participate in discus-

sions, ask questions, and apply what they have learned through hands-on activities or projects.

3.2. *Students’ Interest in Learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City—*

3.2.1. *Self-Efficacy*—Table 8 shows students’ interest in learning English regarding self-efficacy, described as extensive, with a category mean of 3.51. This means that the students in Bunawan District, Davao City, oftentimes

manifest it. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 4.41 to 3.10. Finding English lessons easy and understandable shows a mean rating of 4.41, which is described as extensive and interpreted as this item always observed by the teachers. Further, the item Doing well in English tests has a mean rating of 3.10, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item sometimes manifested.

Table 8. Students’ Interest in Learning English in Terms of Self-Efficacy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Finding the English lessons easy and understandable.	4.14	Extensive
Doing well in English tests.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Answering English activities by myself.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.51	Extensive

This implies that students are confident that they can engage effectively with English, acquire language skills, and maintain a strong interest in learning. The result agrees with Gun and Yildiz’s (2014) assertion that students with high self-efficacy have a positive self-image regarding their language skills, encouraging them to stay interested and motivated. They are proactive in seeking out and utilizing resources for language learning. They take ownership of their learning process. This also supports the idea of Aurah (2017) that high self-efficacy encourages students to believe in their ability to learn

English, which, in turn, boosts their motivation and interest in the subject. They are more likely to set and achieve specific goals related to English language learning. They are confident in their ability to work towards these goals.

3.2.2. *Active Learning Activities*—This domain of students’ interest in learning English in terms of active learning activities, as shown in Table 9, reflects an extensive category mean of 3.46, which means that the respondents in Bunawan District, Davao City, oftentimes manifest it. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 4.13 to 2.85.

The table further reveals that the item Finding relevant resources that will help me when I do not understand an English concept has a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Meanwhile, the item Connecting my previous knowledge to the new topic in English has a mean rating of 2.85, described

as moderately extensive and interpreted as students’ interest in learning English is sometimes manifested. This implies that the teaching methods and strategies that require students to actively engage with the language and its content are often manifested. This is congruent with the view of Kubischta (2014) that active learning activities capture students’ attention and encour-

Table 9. Students’ Interest in Learning English in Terms of Active Learning Activities

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Connecting my previous knowledge to a new topic in English.	2.85	Moderately Extensive
Discussing with the teacher or other students to clarify my understanding when I do not understand a concept in English.	3.49	Extensive
Trying to find out why when I make a mistake in English class activities.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Finding relevant resources that will help me when I do not understand an English concept.	4.13	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.46	Extensive

age them to participate actively in the learning process, increasing their overall engagement. Active activities provide students ample opportunities to practice and improve their language skills in real-life contexts. Moreover, the result corroborates Bramucci’s (2013) findings that active learning activities can be intrinsically exciting and enjoyable, stimulating students’ cu-

riosity and interest in the English language.

3.2.3. *Learning Value*—As shown in Table 10, this domain has a category mean of 3.44, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted that this domain of students’ interest in learning English is sometimes manifested. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.74 to 2.98.

Table 10. Students’ Interest in Learning English in Terms of Learning Value

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Thinking that learning English is important because it is useful in my daily life.	3.60	Extensive
Thinking that learning English is important because it stimulates thinking.	2.98	Moderately Extensive
I think that learning English is important because it helps me learn to solve problems.	3.43	Extensive
Class gives me the opportunity to answer questions in my mind.	3.74	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.44	Extensive

Specifically, the item Class gives me the opportunity to answer questions in my mind has a mean rating of 3.74, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the teachers. The item Thinking that learning English is important because it stimulates thinking reflects a mean rating of 2.98, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested by the teachers in Bunawan District, Davao City. The result

indicates that students see English as a valuable skill and a meaningful part of their education. The result supports the assertion of Altındağ and Senemoğlu (2013) that high learning value inspires students to be motivated and actively engaged in learning English, as they recognize its significance in their lives. When students believe that learning English is intrinsically valuable, their natural curiosity and interest in the language are more likely to be sustained. This

also supports Granito and Chernobilsky’s (2012) idea that students with high learning value are more inclined to set and work towards specific language learning goals, as they understand the importance of achieving proficiency.

3.2.4. *Performance Goal*—Table 11 shows Students’ interest in learning English in terms of performance goals was described as extensive, with a category mean of 3.64. This means that the student’s interest in learning English is often-times manifested by the respondents. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 4.51 to

3.18. The item I participate in the English class activities not to compete with my classmates but to learn together and to share ideas shows a mean rating of 4.51, described as extensive and interpreted as this item always observed by the teachers. Further, the item I participated in in the English class activities not only to get good grades but also to learn new things has a mean rating of 3.18, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item sometimes manifested.

Table 11. Students’ Interest in Learning English in Terms of Performance Goal

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Participating in English class activities not only to get good grades but also to learn new things.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Participating in the English class activities not to compete with my classmates but to learn together and to share ideas.	4.51	Very Extensive
Participating in the English class activities not to impress my teacher but to fulfill my curiosity.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.64	Extensive

This implies that students set clear targets for their language skills and academic achievements. The result is congruent with Guido and Dela Cruz’s (2011) conclusion that high-performance goals provide students with a clear direction and purpose in their English language learning, as they know what they aim to achieve. They often invest focused effort and dedication to attain their language proficiency and academic objectives in English. This also supports the idea of Akomolafe and Adesua (2015) that performance goals encourage students to monitor their progress regularly, which can lead to more effective and targeted language improvement.

3.2.5. *Learning Environmental Goal*—This domain of students’ interest in learning English, as shown in Table 12, reflects a moderately extensive category mean of 3.14, which means that the respondents in Bunawan District,

Davao City sometimes manifest it. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.64 to 2.78. The table further reveals that the item Being willing to participate in the English class because I am given the opportunity to express my idea has a mean rating of 3.64, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Meanwhile, the item Being interested in participating in the English class activities because the teacher gives me enough time to complete the task has a mean rating of 2.78, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as students’ interest in learning English is sometimes manifested. This suggests that the learning environment empowers students with an average interest to believe in their ability to succeed in learning English and take control of their language learning journey. Adding more, the result supports the idea of Akomolafe and

Adesua (2015) that setting learning environmental goals encourages educators to create a more conducive and supportive atmosphere for students, which is especially beneficial for those with average levels of interest in learning En-

glish. This is congruent with Taylor’s (2014) idea that a well-designed learning environment can help boost students’ engagement with average levels of interest in English, making the learning process more appealing.

Table 12. Students’ Interest in Learning English in Terms of Learning Environment Goal

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Being willing to participate in the class because the topics are exciting and challenging.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
Being willing to participate in the English class because I am given the opportunity to express my ideas.	3.64	Extensive
I am interested in participating in the English class activities because the teacher gives me enough time to complete the task.	2.78	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.14	Moderately Extensive

Lastly, Table 13 shows the summary of students’ interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City. As shown in the table, students’ interest in learning English obtained an overall mean score of 3.51 with a descriptive rating of extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the teachers. Adding more, results in Table 13 show that students’ interest in learning English in terms of performance goal acquired the highest mean score of 3.64, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while students’ interest in learning English in terms of Learning environment simulation acquire the lowest mean score of 3.14 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested among teachers. The result implies that students are eager to participate in language-related activities,

seek opportunities for language development, and actively engage with the language both in and out of the classroom. This supports the idea of Zeidan and Jayosi (2015) that students with high interest are naturally more motivated to learn English, making them more engaged in the learning process. High levels of interest often result in greater effort and dedication, leading to improved language proficiency. This is similar to Wiliam’s (2011) findings that students’ interest in learning English is not only a valuable educational goal but also a key to personal and professional success in an increasingly interconnected world. It opens doors to opportunities and enriches their lives in multiple ways, enabling them to engage in global conversations, expand their horizons, and contribute to a more inclusive and diverse society.

3.3. *Relationship Between Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies and Students’ Interest in Learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City*—The results of the analysis of the relationship between teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies and students’ interest in learning English in Bunawan District in

Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between the mentioned variables. Table 14 shows that school-based training has a significant positive relationship with the learning organization skills of teachers in Bunawan District, Davao

Table 13. Summary on Students’ Interest in Learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Self-efficacy	3.51	Extensive
Active learning strategies	3.46	Extensive
Learning values	3.44	Extensive
Performance goal	3.64	Extensive
Learning environment simulation	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.51	Extensive

City, with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.568, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies changes, students’ interest in learning English also changes significantly. Adding more, results on the table show that teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies of teachers in terms of classroom interaction; learning engagement; skills development; time consciousness; learning attention and a conducive environment have a significant positive relationship with the student’s interest in learning English with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.330, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.413, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.352, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.562, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.365, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.342, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 14. Correlation Table: Students’ Interest in Learning English

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Classroom Interaction	0.330*	0.000	Reject H0
Learning Engagement	0.413*	0.000	Reject H0
Skills Development	0.352*	0.000	Reject H0
Time Consciousness	0.562*	0.000	Reject H0
Learning Attention	0.365*	0.000	Reject H0
Conducive Environment	0.342*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Teachers’ Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies	0.568*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 < r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 < r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$

This implies that teachers’ interactive-direct teaching strategies create a more engaging and dynamic learning environment that fosters students’ interest in learning English. The result agrees with Milner et al.’s (2012) contention that interactive teaching encourages students to practice and improve their communication skills in English. Students becoming more proficient in expressing themselves often find the language more interesting and valuable. Additionally, this

is congruent with the view of Saeed and Zyngier (2012) that interactive teaching often involves the exploration of English-speaking cultures, literature, and media. This exposure can pique students' curiosity and interest in the cultural aspects of the language. It increases students' motivation to participate actively in class.

3.4. *Influence of Teachers' Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies on the Students' Interest in Learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City*—The significance of the influence of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies on students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City, was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 15 shows that when teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, time consciousness, learning Attention, and conducive environment are considered predictors of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies, the model is significant, as evident in F-value of 110.650 with $p < 0.05$. Therefore, teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies predict the students' interest in learning English

in Bunawan District, Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.446 indicates that teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies have contributed significantly to the variability of students' interest in learning English by 44.60. In addition, table 15 shows that there are domains of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies that significantly influence the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City. This table also indicates that teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies regarding classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, learning attention, and conducive environment are significant when the predictors are considered. This means that the extent of students' interest in learning English increases by 0.157, 0.290, 0.115, 0.218, and 0.169 for each unit increase in teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies significantly influence the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City.

Table 15. Influence of Teachers' Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies on the Students' Interest in Learning English in Bunawan District, Davao City

Variables	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Classroom Interaction	.157*	.150	.046	.000	Reject H0
Learning Engagement	.290*	.319	.051	.000	Reject H0
Skills Development	.115*	.323	.047	.000	Reject H0
Time Consciousness	-.020	.108	.003	.112	Accept H0
Learning Attention	.218*	.230	.042	.001	Reject H0
Conducive Environment	.169*	.167	.063	.000	Reject H0

R2 = 0.446

F-value = 110.650*

p-value = 0.000

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

This affirmed that interactive teaching strategies undeniably improved the students' interest in learning English. The result is congruent

with the view of Cetin-Dindar (2016) that interactive teaching strategies, such as group discussions, debates, and hands-on activities, ac-

tively engage students in the learning process. Students are more likely to stay interested and focused on the subject when actively involved. It often connects English language learning to real-world situations, making the content more relevant and meaningful to students. This helps students see the practical applications of the lan-

guage, increasing their interest. This also corroborates with Jorde and Dillon's (2012) idea that interactive teaching can incorporate technology, such as language-learning apps, multimedia resources, and online language exercises. Technology use often aligns with modern students' interests and preferences.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The literature supported the discussions in the first chapters, and the conclusions were based on the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of teachers' interactive teaching strategies significantly influence students' interest in learning English utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 156 elementary school teachers in Bunawan District in Davao City as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in Bunawan District, Davao City, got an overall mean of 3.36 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, time consciousness, learning attention, and conducive environment obtained mean scores of 3.21, 3.41, 3.27, 3.45, 3.32, and 3.53, respectively. Students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.51, with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, students' interest in learning English in terms of self-efficacy, active learning strategies, learning values, performance goals, and learning environ-

ment simulation obtained mean scores of 3.51, 3.46, 3.44, 3.64, and 3.14, respectively. Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies have a significant positive relationship with the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .568, p < 0.05$). Teachers' Interactive-Direct Teaching Strategies regarding classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, learning attention, and conducive environment significantly influenced the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City, as evidenced by the F-value of 110.650 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.446 indicated that teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies had contributed significantly to the variability of the student's interest in learning English by 44.40

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in Bunawan District, Davao City, were moderately extensive. Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in terms of classroom interaction, skills development, and learning attention obtained moderately extensive descriptive ratings, while teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in learning engagement, time consciousness, and conducive

environment obtained moderately extensive descriptive ratings. This implies that the balance between teacher guidance and student involvement falls somewhere in the middle, offering a well-rounded approach to instruction. Students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City was rated as extensive. Students' interest in learning English regarding self-efficacy, active learning strategies, learning values, and performance goals belong to moderately extensive ratings. In contrast, student's interest in learning English in a learning environment simulation acquired moderately extensive ratings. This implies that students are eager to participate in language-related activities, seek opportunities for language development, and actively engage with the language both in and out of the classroom. Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies have a significant positive relationship with students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City. This means that as the extent of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies changes, students' interest in learning English also significantly changes. This implies that teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies create a more engaging and dynamic learning environment that fosters students' interest in learning English. Teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in planning, instruction, and management significantly influenced the students' interest in learning English in Bunawan District in Davao City. This affirmed that students' interest in learning English is a function

of teachers' interactive-direct teaching strategies in Bunawan District in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education may develop policies that ensure equitable access to English language education, regardless of socioeconomic background or geographic location. Additionally, DepEd may implement standardized assessments to measure language proficiency and regularly monitor the effectiveness of language programs. School heads may promote continuous professional development for English teachers, allowing them to stay updated on modern teaching techniques and strategies. They may foster a positive and inclusive learning environment by encouraging students to engage actively in English language learning. English teachers may seek out opportunities for professional development to improve teaching skills and stay updated on language education trends. Adding more, they should introduce students to English-speaking cultures, literature, and media to make language learning more engaging and relevant. Students may actively participate in English language classes, engage in discussions, and seek opportunities to practice and use the language. Moreover, they may immerse themselves in English-speaking environments to apply and reinforce their language skills whenever possible. Future researchers may engage in action research projects that involve collaboration with educators and policymakers to implement and evaluate innovative language education strategies.

5. References

- Agbabi, C. O., Onyeike, V. C., & Wali, W. I. (2013). *Classroom management: A practical approach*. University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Agsalog, M. (2019). Experiential learning approach: Its effects on the academic performance and motivation to learn physics of grade 10 students. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9(9), 844–850. <http://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-0919/ijsrp-p93113.pdf>

- Ahmad, C. N. C., Ching, W. C., Yahaya, A., & Abdullah, M. F. N. L. (2015). Relationship between constructivist learning environments and educational facility in science classrooms. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 191, 1952–1957. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.672>
- Akomolafe, C., & Adesua, V. (2015). The classroom environment: A major motivating factor towards the high academic performance of senior secondary school students in south west nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(34), 17–21. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1086098.pdf>
- Albalate, A., Larcia, H., & Jaen, J. (2018). Students' motivation towards science learning of stem students of the university of batangas, lipa city. <https://www.grdspublishing.org/index.php/people/article/view/1045/910>
- Alkin, S. (2013). *Evaluation of elementary school teachers' behaviors of supporting critical thinking* [Unpublished doctoral thesis]. Ankara University Institute of Education Sciences.
- Alsaleh, N. (2020). Teaching critical thinking skills: A literature review. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 19(1), 21–39. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1239945.pdf>
- Alt, D. (2014). Contemporary constructivist practices in higher education settings and academic motivational factors. *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 56(3), 374–400. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1120641.pdf>
- Altındağ, M., & Senemoğlu, N. (2013). Metacognitive skills scale. *Hacettepe University Journal of Education*, 28(1), 15–26. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/296839320_METACOGNITIVE_SKILLS_SCALE
- Alzahrani, I., & Woollard, J. (2013). The role of the constructivist learning theory and collaborative learning environment on wiki classroom, and the relationship between them. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED539416.pdf>
- Andersson, H. (2017). *Möten där vi blir sedda: En studie om elevers engagemang i skolan* [Diss.]. Malmö: Malmö högskola.
- Andressa, H., Mavrikaki, E., & Dermizaki, I. (2015). Adaptation of the student's motivation toward science learning questionnaire to measure greek students' motivation towards biology learning. *International Journal Of Biology Education*, 4(2), 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.20876/ijobed.56334>
- Aregu, B. B. (2013). Enhancing self-regulated learning in teaching spoken communication: Does it affect speaking efficacy and performance? *Journal Foreign Language Teaching*, 10(1), 96–109. <https://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/v10n12013/aregu.pdf>
- Aurah, C. (2017). Investigating the relationship between science self-efficacy beliefs, gender, and academic achievement, among high school students in kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(8), 146–153. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1139069.pdf>
- Bas, G. (2013). Students' views on the constructivist learning environment in elementary schools: A qualitative inquiry. *Cukurova University Faculty of Education Journal*, 42(2), 64–86. <https://arastirmax.com/en/publication/cukurova-universitesi-egitim-fakultesi-dergisi/42/2/students-views-constructivist-learning-environment-elementary-schools-qualitative-inquiry/arid/166e54c8-7b6b-4069>
- Basheer, A. N. A. (2014). Teachers' perceptions about constructivist learning in afghan schools. mathematics teachers' perceptions and usage of question-answer, individual and group

- work methods considering constructivism. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:812318/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Bawa, N., & Zubairu, S. (2015). Constructivism and classroom interaction. *International Journal of Modern Social Sciences*, 4(2), 71–81. <http://modernscientificpress.com/Journals/ViewArticle.aspx?YTDXIp8pwb35qABc+2BV/9NitZguWvfvF7Zvj1+sSSDpLasVfL2uW4xG0GShqTPF>
- Bay, E., Bagececi, B., & Cetin, B. (2013). The effects of the social constructivist approach on the learners' problem-solving and metacognitive levels. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(3), 343–349. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/25850948.pdf>
- Blazar, D. (2016). *Teacher and teaching effects on students' academic performance, attitudes, and behaviors*. <https://dash.harvard.edu/bitstream/handle/1/27112692/BLAZAR-DISSERTATION-2016.pdf?sequence=1>
- Bramucci, A. (2013). *Self-regulated learning. theories and potential applications in didactics*. http://intelligent-tutor.eu/files/2012/06/I-TUTOR_supportmaterial_self-regulated_learning_EN.pdf
- Brown, B. (2014). *The impact of self-efficacy and motivation characteristics on the academic achievement of upward bound participants*. <https://aquila.usm.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1429&context=dissertations>
- Brown, P., Mccord, R., Matusovich, H., & Kajfez, R. (2014). The use of motivation theory in engineering education research: A systematic review of literature. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 23, 1–20. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03043797.2014.941339>
- Canvas, P. (2012). Factor affecting the motivation of turkish primary students for science learning. *Science Education International*, 22(1), 31–42. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ941653>
- Cardelús, E. (2015). *Motivationen, attityder och moderna språk: En studie om elevers motivationsprocesser och attityder vid studier och lärande av moderna språk*. Stockholms universitet.
- Chan, Y. L., & Norlizah, C. H. (2017). Students' motivation towards science learning and students' science achievement. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 6(4), 174–189. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/0598/7fd7aec616c39e2eb21403f19e4231d283a8.pdf>
- Chow, S. J., & Yong, B. C. S. (2013). Secondary school students' motivation and achievement in combined science. *US-China Education Review*, 3(4), 213–228. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED542966.pdf>
- Chumbley, S. B., Haynes, C., & Stofer, K. A. (2015). A measure of students' motivation to learn science through agricultural stem emphasis. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 56(4), 107–122. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1122894.pdf>
- Cirik, I., Colak, E., & Kaya, D. (2013). Constructivist learning environment: The teachers and students perspectives. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*, 6(2), 30–44. <http://www.ijonte.org/FileUpload/ks63207/File/03.cirik.pdf>
- Clark, T. D. (2014). *How to manage stress in college* (Vol. 1). TDC Enterprise. <https://www.free-ebooks.net/self-improvement/How-to-Manage-Stress-In-College-Study-Skills-and-Still-Have-Loads-Of-Fun-Vol-1/pdf?dl&preview>

- Clinkenbeard, P. R. (2012). Motivation and gifted students: Implications of theory and research. *Psychology in the Schools, 49*(7), 622–630. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/pits.21628>
- Cooper, K., & White, R. (2012). *Qualitative research in the post-modern era: Contexts of qualitative research*. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9789400723382>
- Cunningham, K. R. (2013). *The effect of motivation on student success in a first-year experience course*. <http://digitalcommons.wku.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1040&context=dis>
- Evans, C. (2014). *Exploring the use of a deep approach to learning with students in the process of learning to teach*. <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/374302/>
- Fenning, B., & May, L. (2013). Where there is a will, there is an a: Examining the roles of self-efficacy and self-concept in college students' current educational attainment and career planning. *Social Psychology of Education, 16*(4), 21–30. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1039406>
- Fox, J., & Schirmacher, R. (2012). *Art and creative development for young children*. <https://www.cengage.com/c/art-and-creative-development-for-young-children-8e-fox/9781285432380>
- Gee, J. (2013). *Importance of prior knowledge to learning*. <https://news.illinoisstate.edu/2012/01/importance-of-prior-knowledge-to-learning/>
- Gibbens, B. (2019). Measuring student motivation in an introductory biology class [Retrieved from <https://online.ucpress.edu/abt/article/81/1/20/91855/Measuring-Student-Motivation-in-an-Introductory>].
- Glynn, S. M., Brickman, P., Armstrong, N., & Taasoobshirazi, G. (2013). Science motivation questionnaire ii: Validation with science majors and nonscience majors [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.20442>]. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching, 48*(10), 1159–1176.
- Granito, M., & Chernobilsky, E. (2012). The effect of technology on a student' s motivation and knowledge retention [Retrieved from https://opencommons.uconn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1016&context=nera_2012].
- Guido, R. (2013). Attitude and motivation towards learning physics [Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1805/1805.02293.pdf>]. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, 2*(11), 95–111.
- Gurses, A., Demiray, S., & Dogar, C. (2015). A design practice for interactive-direct teaching based on constructivist learning (idtbel): Dissolution and solutions [Retrieved from <http://doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.244>]. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 191*, 44–49.
- Harding, S. M. (2019). Self-regulated learning as a predictor of mathematics and reading performance: A picture of students in grades 5 to 8 [Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0004944119830153>].
- Hubert, B. (2017). Cognitive self-regulation and social functioning among french children: A longitudinal study from kindergarten to first grade [Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/pchj.160>].
- Hurst, B., Wallace, R., & Nixon, S. (2013). The impact of social interaction on student learning [Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3105&>

- context=reading horizons]. *Reading Horizons: A Journal of Literacy and Language Arts*, 52(4), 375–398.
- Kwan, Y. W., & Wong, A. F. L. (2014). The constructivist classroom learning environment and its associations with critical thinking ability of secondary school students in liberal studies [Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10984-014-9158-x>]. *Learning Environments Research*, 17, 191–207.
- Laurillard, D. (2012). *Teaching as a design science. building pedagogical patterns for learning and technology* [E-book]. Routledge.
- Lawson, M. A., & Lawson, H. A. (2013). New conceptual frameworks for student engagement research, policy, and practice [Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.3102/0034654313480891>].
- Lemley, J. B., Schumacher, G., & Vesey, W. (2014). What learning environments best address 21st -century students' perceived needs at the secondary level of instruction? *NASSP Bulletin*, 98(2), 101–125.
- Linnenbrink-Garcia, L., Patall, E., & Pektrun, R. (2016). Adaptive motivation and emotion in education: Research and principles for instructional design [Retrieved from https://selfdeterminationtheory.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/2016_Linnenbrink-GarciaPatallPektrun.ClimateMotiveEmo.pdf]. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 3(2), 228–236.
- Llego, J. (2017). Classroom management approach of ste science teachers in region 1 philippines [Retrieved from <https://www.onlinejournal.in/IJIRV3I3/314.pdf>].
- Mbatha, S. (2015). The relationship between self-efficacy, motivation, and academic performance among students from various gender and generational groups [Retrieved from <http://scholar.ufs.ac.za:8080/xmlui/bitstream/handle/11660/4592/MbathaS.pdf?sequence=1>].
- Michaelis, J. (2015). The role of interest and motivation in science investigation and engineering design instruction [Retrieved from https://sites.nationalacademies.org/cs/groups/dbassesite/documents/web/page/dbasse_182819.pdf].
- Milner, A. R., Templin, M. A., & Czerniak, C. M. (2012). Elementary science students' motivation and learning strategy use: Constructivist classroom contextual factors in a life science laboratory and a traditional classroom. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 22(2), 151–170. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ913429>
- Mubeen, S., & Reid, N. (2014). The measurement of motivation with science students. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 3(3), 129–144. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1086038.pdf>
- Mutlu, G., & Güler, C. (2017). Authentic instruction: Efl teachers' perspectives. *European Conference on Educational Research (ECER 2017) of the European Educational Research Association*. <http://www.eera-ecer.de/ecer-programmes/conference/22/contribution/41901/>
- Nasiriyani, A., Azar, H. K., Noruzy, A., & Dalvand, M. R. (2012). A model of self-efficacy, task value, achievement goals, effort and mathematics achievement. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 3(2), 612–618.
- Ozerem, A., & Akkoyunlu, B. (2015). Learning environments designed according to learning styles and its effects on mathematics achievement. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 61, 61–80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2015.61.4>

- Panadero, E. (2017). A review of self-regulated learning: Six models and four directions for research. <http://doi:10.3389/fpsyg00422>
- Parsons, J., & Taylor, L. (2012). Improving student engagement. *Current Issues in Education*, 14, 1–32. <http://cie.asu.edu/ojs/index.php/cieatasu/article/viewFile/745/162>
- Ruey, S. (2012). A case study of constructivist strategies for adult online learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 41(5), 706–720. <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2009.00965.x>
- Saeed, S., & Zyngier, D. (2012). How motivation influences student engagement: A qualitative case study. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 1(2), 12–17. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1081372.pdf>
- Sever, M., Ulubey, Ö., Toraman, Ç., & Türe, E. (2014). An analysis of high school students' classroom engagement in relation to various variables. *Education and Science*, 39(176), 183–198. <https://doi.org/10.15390/EB.2014.3633>
- Soyogul, E. C. (2015). Students' motivational beliefs and learning strategies: An investigation of the scholar development program. <http://www.thesis.bilkent.edu.tr/0006876.pdf>
- Taylor, E. (2014). The correlation between self-efficacy and the academic success of students. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/58825904.pdf>
- Tuan, H. L., Chin, C. C., & Shieh, S. H. (2005). The development of a questionnaire to measure students' motivation towards science learning. <http://www.ntcu.edu.tw/chin/file/29.pdf>
- Tunca, N. (2015). The regression level of constructivist learning environment characteristics on classroom environment characteristics supporting critical thinking. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 60, 181–200. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1076652.pdf>
- Wiliam, D. (2011). *Embedded formative assessment*. Solution Tree Press.
- Wood, R. (2019). Students' motivation to engage with science learning activities through the lens of self-determination theory: Results from a single-case school-based study. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 15(7), 8–29. <https://www.ejmste.com/download/students-motivation-to-engage-with-science-learning-activities-through-the-lens-of-7677.pdf>
- Yildirim, M. C. (2014). Developing a scale for constructivist learning environment management skills. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 54, 1–18. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1057216.pdf>
- Yliportimo, T. (2016). Students' meaningful learning experiences during an outdoor course in chile. <https://jyx.jyu.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/50527/1/URN%3ANBN%3Afi%3Ajyu-201606213288.pdf>
- Zeidan, A. H., & Jayosi, M. R. (2015). Science process skills and attitudes toward science among palestinian secondary school students. *World Journal of Education*, 5(1), 14–24. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1158460.pdf>
- Zhu, Y., & Leung, F. K. S. (2012). Motivation and achievement: Is there an east asian model? *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 9, 1189–1212. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10763-010-9255-y>